

[Paul Zogala](#), born in 1988, is a Canadian who works as a Trader at Murchinson, a global investment firm with a multi-strategic investment approach, founded in 2012.

In 2014, he received a Bachelor of Arts (with honors) in Economics from McMaster University. Murchinson employed him until 2016. He assists investors by structuring and negotiating investments, convertible securities, debt instruments, and warrants.

Murchinson is a multinational investment firm that employs a multi-strategy investment strategy. Because of the importance of all parts of the capital structure, experienced [Chartered Market Technician and CFA Charterholder](#) Paul Zogala, orchestrates and manages investments using [stocks](#), convertible securities, debt instruments, and warrants. In addition to fundamental and technical analysis, he uses both practical and quantitative analysis to construct and monitor portfolio holdings. He manages the portfolio and implements corporate action plans.